
EFFECTS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION ON ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS OF UNDERGRADUATES IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

¹Dr. Ayotunde Adewale ADEYEMI and ²Professor A. S. BAMIRE

¹Department of Agricultural Education, Osun State College of Education Ila-Orangun

²Department of Agricultural Economics, Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife

E-mail: aaadeyemi@ossceila.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Countries all over the world have initiated the policy of promoting the supply of entrepreneurs in order to reduce the rate of unemployment and promote economic growth especially through the introduction of entrepreneurship education. The Federal Government of Nigeria in collaboration with the Nigerian University Commission (NUC) has also introduced the entrepreneurship Education into the tertiary school curriculum in order to reduce the effect of unemployment among youths. This research was initiated to verify the efficacy of this policy in stimulating entrepreneurial intentions among the youths in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the level of entrepreneurship skills possessed by the students and their perception of entrepreneurship education; it further investigated the career choice of the students and finally examined the effect of entrepreneurship education on students' intentions towards entrepreneurship. This was with a view to understanding the outcome of entrepreneurship education course on students' career choice in Nigeria. The study made use of Primary data collected from undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences from three (3) universities namely; Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) Ile-Ife, Federal University of Technology, Akure and University of Ibadan. A well structured questionnaire was administered purposively to 540 students from the three (3) universities and analyzed using descriptive and logistic regression methods. The study found that the undergraduate students possess greater entrepreneurial competencies in three major areas which include: identifying business opportunity, networking and risk taking out of the twenty three (23) entrepreneurial skills identified. Using a five (5) point rating scale, the study found that 51.3% of the students indicated that entrepreneurship course was useful, 28% indicated that it was very useful, 14.8% were indifferent, 3% indicated that it was un-useful while 2.6% of the students stated that the course was very un-useful. On the career choice of the students, 25% indicated a very high prospects of working in Federal Civil Service, 16.9% showed very high prospect of securing a job in a financial Institutions while 17.6% opted for a job in Oil and Gas sector. In terms of student intention to become self employed, fifty two percent (52%) indicated their intentions toward self-employment after graduation while forty-two (42%) do not. Finally, the factors that were found to be determining entrepreneurial intentions among the students include Gender ($t=2.79, p<0.05$), Religion ($t=2.86, p<0.01$), Family Position ($t=2.79, p<0.01$), Institutions (OAU ($t=4.48, p<0.01$), Unibadan ($t=2.86, p<0.05$), Departments (Geography ($t=2.45, p<0.05$), Political Sciences ($t=5.47, p<0.01$), Sociology ($t=3.27, p<0.01$), Federal Civil Service ($t=2.28, p<0.1$), Academic Performance ($t=2.14, p<0.1$) and Experience ($t=2.17, p<0.1$). In this study, entrepreneurship education

has a positive impact on students' entrepreneurial intentions but it was not significant. The study concluded that although, entrepreneurship education had positive impact on the students' entrepreneurial intentions, however it was not a significant factor motivating the students into entrepreneurial related activities after graduation. The study therefore recommended urgent government intervention in providing enabling environment for entrepreneurship education policy to thrive in Nigeria.

Keywords: Effects, Entrepreneurial Education, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Undergraduates, Nigerian universities and Southwest, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

For over 40 years now, researchers have tried to examine the various characteristics and influences of entrepreneurs (Gartner, 2018; Shane and Venkatamaran, 2020; Baron, 2014). Their efforts identified various factors responsible for economic agents taking up entrepreneurial activities, and why some do not (Kuratko, 2013). Studies in the field of entrepreneurship also show that arguments exist as a result of the assertions that entrepreneurs are born or made through training and education. The view that entrepreneurs are made is also supported by the human capital theory (Franke and Luthje, 2018).

The human capital theory states that higher education provides individuals with skills and higher ability, which leads to more productive and efficient activity and the introduction of entrepreneurship education as a scholarly field in tertiary institutions all over the world. Studies into the field of entrepreneurship support the view that entrepreneurship education promotes entrepreneurial intention amongst students in the tertiary institutions. Some suggest that there is a negative relationship (Krugger and Reilly, 2022; Autio *et al.*, 2021; Kuratko, 2013; Peterman and Kennedy, 2022; Franke and Luthje, 2018), and some studies are inconclusive (Hosseini *et al.*, 2020)

Studies into the field of entrepreneurship in developed nations indicated that the entrepreneurship education course has a large impact on students' entrepreneurship founding decision (Clark *et al.*, 2023; McMullan, Long and Wilson, 2015; Katz, 2013). For example, studies in Europe indicated that entrepreneurship course, provided an incentive to business start up with ease and accelerate graduates entrepreneurship founding activities (Brown, 2010), initiated a very important impact on students' subsequently career choice (Fleming, 2004). However, studies in France, Finland and Portugal produced a negative result, meaning that entrepreneurship education does not stimulate entrepreneurial interest among the students (McMullan, Long and Wilson, 2015).

Empirical studies in the field of entrepreneurship education from developing nations are quite scanty when compared to US and other developed countries in Europe and Asia. This is an indication of the late introduction of entrepreneurship education experienced in these countries. However, there are some literatures that pointed out an increased interest in Asia and African countries (Dana, 2021 and Mitra and Matlay, 2014). Furthermore, there is evidence that entrepreneurship education course are becoming more and more common in undergraduates and postgraduates' curriculum.

Studies in Asian and the Scandinavians countries indicated that positive relationship exists between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intentions. The studies has concluded that entrepreneurial intention stimulates entrepreneurial intention among the students (Li *et al.*, 2023) while studies in Iran, Finland and Pakistan concluded that a decline in entrepreneurial intention exists among the students and that entrepreneurial knowledge is

insignificant to entrepreneurial intentions. Based on the results of the above findings, it is quite obvious that the conclusions are mixed across literatures.

In Africa, there have been fewer studies in the field of entrepreneurship education as compared to other continents. In Egypt, Kirby and Ibrahim (2021) conducted a survey into three faculties in the British university. They concluded that most of the students were confused over what an entrepreneur does while, majority wanted a career in a multi-national enterprise than to be self-employed. However, Owasu-Ansah (2018), reported that exposure to entrepreneurship education has a positive influence on the students' career intentions in Ghana.

The situation in Nigeria is not so different from other African countries in terms of attention given to entrepreneurship education. Some of the literatures are mostly theoretical with less attention given to empirical analysis (Aladekomo, 2014;) while the empirical studies concluded that entrepreneurship education promotes entrepreneurial intentions among the students (Bassy and Olu, 2018; Izedonmi and Okafor, 2020; Ifedili and Ofoegbu, 2016). However, most of these studies suffer from several setbacks such as a lack of proper definition of variables that capture entrepreneurial intention. Some were also highly restricted to states in Nigeria and their results are capable of being biased if it were generalized. Some of these studies did not consider the students' entrepreneurial intentions or assess the entrepreneurial course the students were exposed to so as to have a firm knowledge on the delivery process of the course, but were restricted to the management and the administration of entrepreneurship education.

One major study in the field of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria is that of Hosseini *et al.* (2020) which carried out a survey on the determinants of entrepreneurial propensity of Nigerian undergraduates and also formulated a hypothesis to test the impact of entrepreneurship education on the students' intention for entrepreneurial activity. They found that entrepreneurship education spurs students to venture into entrepreneurial activities. Their results seem too superficial because how entrepreneurial intention was measured in their research was not clearly stated in their model. The mere fact that more people are willing to become entrepreneurs does not mean it was caused by entrepreneurship education, hence, the essence of this study. So, there is a need to verify their findings because according to Global Entrepreneurship Monitor's (2018) classification of nations, developing nations like Nigeria was classified as a factor driven nation and for entrepreneurial activities to thrive in such an economy, the government's focus should be the provision of a basic foundation that will lead to entrepreneurship takeoff such as a stable government, basic infrastructure and primary health care which seem not to be fully established in Nigeria.

None of these studies specifically provided a clear measure of entrepreneurship education in their models. It can be inferred from their conclusions that the willingness to become an entrepreneur is entrepreneurship education, but this cannot be totally said to be true. This study, therefore gives a clearer view on this. Thus, based on the problem stated above, the present study provides answers to the following research questions:

- i) Does the level of entrepreneurial skills determine intention among undergraduates?
- ii) What are the perceptions of students towards entrepreneurship education?
- iii) What is the impact of entrepreneurship education on the intention of the undergraduates to take to entrepreneurship?

Objectives of the study

The broad aim of this study is to examine the influence of entrepreneurship education on the motivation of students in becoming entrepreneurs.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i) examine the level of entrepreneurial skills among the undergraduates
- ii) determine the perception of the students toward entrepreneurship education
- iii) examine the career choice of the students, and
- iv) determine the effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial choice of students

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Area of Study

The study was carried out in the Southwestern geo-political zone of Nigeria. Southwestern Nigeria lies between longitude 2^o 42' and 6^o 03' East of Greenwich and latitude 5^o 49' and 9^o 17' North of the equator. The Southwest comprises Osun, Ogun, Ondo, Ekiti, Oyo, and Lagos States. Three states were selected (Osun, Ondo and Oyo) based on the approved number of both public and private universities by National Universities Commission (NUC). Undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences from three (3) universities namely; Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) Ile-Ife, Federal University of Technology, Akure and University of Ibadan.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed for the selection of the respondents for the study. In the first stage, purposive sampling was used to select three states and three universities from Southwestern Nigeria based on their prominence in entrepreneurship education. Preliminary investigation revealed that these universities have started implementing the entrepreneurship education. In the second stage, faculty of social sciences was selected purposively per university based on their involvement in entrepreneurship education. In the third stage, 40 undergraduates and five departments per faculty of social sciences per university were randomly selected to a total number of six hundred undergraduates for the study.

Method of data collection and analysis

The study made use of Primary data collected from undergraduate students of the Faculty of Social Sciences from three (3) universities namely; Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) Ile-Ife, Federal University of Technology, Akure and University of Ibadan. A well structured questionnaire was administered purposively to 540 students from the three (3) universities and analyzed using descriptive and logistic regression methods. This study focused on the final year students of Faculty of Social Sciences in three major universities in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

Information on the variables employed in this study is presented in the figure 1

Model Specification

Based on the logit model in equation 3, our model is now specified following the previous works of Malino and Wilson, 2003., Duthje and Franke, 2003) as;

$$\text{Log} \frac{\text{Pro}(E)}{\text{Pro}(\text{none}) - E} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{ demographic factors} + \beta_2 \text{ Contextual factor} + \beta_3 \text{ Psychological traits}$$

$$\text{Log} \frac{\text{Pro}(E)}{\text{Pro}(\text{none}) - E} = \text{Entrepreneurial Intention}$$

Variable taking values of 1 for Yes and 0 for No

α_0 = intercept

Demographic factors are:

- β_{11} = Age
- β_{12} = Gender
- β_{13} = Religion
- β_{14} = Geo-political Zones

- β_{24} = Institutional Influence
- β_{25} = Departmental Influence
- β_{26} = Academic Performance
- β_{27} = Parental Influence
- β_{28} = Job Prospects

β_{15} = Ethnicity

Contextual Factors are:

B_{21} = Entrepreneurship Education

B_{22} = Entrepreneurial Experience

B_{23} = Role Model

Psychological Traits

β_{31} = Creativity

β_{32} = Risk Ability

β_{33} = Innovation

β_{34} = Leadership Ability

Measurement of Data

(a) Dependent Variable

The dependent variable is entrepreneurial intention (EI). This may be regarded as the inclination to venture into entrepreneurial activity after the respondents graduation from school. Entrepreneurial intention was measured by binary variable which assumed a value of '1' if the respondents answered 'Yes' to the question; "In the next five years, please can you indicate your agreement with the statement, I have got firm intention to start a company and '0' otherwise".

(b) Explanatory variables

The independent variables were classified under three categories:

(i) Demographic factors

Age – This variable was measured by grouping it into four (4) age brackets; Age 1 = below 20 years, Age 2 = 20 – 29 years, Age 3 = 30 – 40 years and Age 4 = Above 40. Age 2 was used as a reference group and coded as '1' others '0'

Gender – Male = 1, Female = 0

Religion – Muslim = 1, Others 0, Christians = 1, others 0, Free thinkers = 1, others 0

State – The respondents were asked their state of origin which was group into the Southwest geo-political zones in Nigeria. South/West = 1, others 0;

Ethnicity – Four principal ethnic groups were recognized in this model; Igbo, Yoruba, Hausa and other ethnic minorities. Igbo = 1, otherwise = 0; Yoruba = 1, otherwise = 0; Hausa = 1, otherwise = 0.

The Igbos was used as a reference group.

(ii) Contextual Factors

Entrepreneurship Education – This variable was measured using a 5 point Likert rating scale on the respondents' assessments of the usefulness of Entrepreneurship Education. The responses include; Strongly Agree, Agree, Indifferent, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Those who strongly agreed and agreed were re-coded as '1' while others were coded '0'. This was subsequently incorporated into the regression model as a dichotomy variable to capture the effect of entrepreneurship education (EE) on intention.

Entrepreneurial Experience – This variable was measured using three areas where the respondents may have working experience which include working in Family Business, Self employment or Paid job. Those with self employment experience were coded as '1', while others '0' and similarly to others.

Role Model – Respondents were asked "if they knew any person that had created his/her own company?" Response were coded Yes = '1' and No = '0'.

Departmental Influence- Five (5) departments were used in this model; Economics, Geography, Psychology, Political Science and Sociology. Economics was used as reference

Academic performance- The probable graduating GPA grade was used to determine academic performance. The grade comprises First Class, Second Class Upper, Second Class Lower and Pass. First class, it was used as a reference and coded as '1' while others '0'.

Parental Influence- If the parent owns a business, it was coded '1', while if the parents do not own a business '0'.

Job Prospects- This variable was measured using 5 points rating scale on the respondents probability of securing a job in any of the following sectors after graduation; Financial Institutions, Oil and Gas, Federal and State Civil Service, Academics Non-Governmental Agencies (NGOs) and Parent business. The responses include; very low, low, not really sure, high and very high. Those who indicated high and very high were regarded with high probability (which means that wage is more rewarding than self employment) while otherwise lower probability.

(iii) Psychological Traits

This variable was measured using a five (5) point Likert rating scale on the respondents ability to perform tasks relating to creativity, innovation, risk and leadership responsibilities. The responses include: strongly agree, agree, indifferent, disagree and strongly disagree. Those who agree and strongly agree were coded as '1' others '0'.

This model is described as follows.

Consider two occupations denoted by j : entrepreneurship, E, and paid employment, p. Each individual has a vector characteristics W_i and derives utility,

$$U_{ij} = U(W_i, j) + u_{ij}$$

If they work in occupation j , where $U(.,.)$ utility that can be observed and u_{ij} is the unobserved utility. Denote by z_i a 'latent' variable which measures the relative utility advantage to i of being in occupation E relative to P. That is,

$$Z_i = U(W_i; E) - U(W_i; P) + u_{iE} - u_{iP}$$

If we assume that $U(.,.)$ is linear, taking the form $U(W_i; j) = \beta' j W_i$,

Where β_j are vectors of co-efficients, then we can write

$$Z_i = \alpha + \beta' W_i + v_i,$$

Where $\beta' := \beta'E - \beta'P$ is another vector of coefficients; $\alpha := E[u_{iE} - u_{iP}]$ is an intercept; and $v_i := u_{iE} - u_{iP} - \alpha \sim N(0, \delta^2)$ is a disturbance term. Henceforth, the intercept term is incorporated in W_i as column of ones, so B will be treated as a complete set of co-efficient.

Individual i chooses entrepreneurship over paid employment if $z_i \geq 0$. Hence this defines the observable binary occupational indicator variable

$$z_i := \{1 \text{ if individual is observed in E, i. e., if } z_i \geq 0\}$$

$$z_i := \{0 \text{ if individual } i \text{ is observed in P, i. e., if } z_i < 0\}$$

Therefore the probability that an individual is observed to be an entrepreneur in a representative sample, with characteristic vector W_i , is $\Pr(z_i=1)$ and $\Pr(z_i \geq 0)$

The logit model arises if the distribution function of v_i is assumed to be that of the logistic distribution, in which case (2) becomes

$$\Pr(z_i=1) = \frac{\exp(\beta' W_i)}{1 + \exp(\beta' W_i)}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Factor analysis (Entrepreneurial Competencies)

Variable	
I can see new market opportunities for new products and services	X ₁
I can discover new ways to improve existing products	X ₂
I can identify new areas for potential growth	X ₃
I can see new market opportunities for new products and services	X ₄
I can design products that solve current problems	X ₅
I can create products that fulfil customers' unmet needs.	X ₆
I can bring product concepts to market in a timely manner	X ₇
I can determine what the business will look like	X ₈
I can create a working environment that lets people be more their own boss	X ₉
I can develop a working environment that encourages people to try out something new	X ₁₀
I can design products that solve current problems	X ₁₁
I can encourage people to take initiatives and responsibilities for their ideas and decisions regardless of the outcome	X ₁₂
I can form partner or alliance relationship with others	X ₁₃
I can develop and maintain a favourable relationship with others	X ₁₄
I can develop relationships with key people who are connected to capital sources	X ₁₅
I can identify potential sources of funding for investment	X ₁₆
I can articulate vision and values of the organization	X ₁₇
I can inspire others to embrace vision and values of the company	X ₁₈
I can formulate a set of actions in a pursuit of opportunities	X ₁₉
I can work productively under continuous stress, pressure and conflict	X ₂₀
I can tolerate unexpected changes in business conditions	X ₂₁
I can persist in the face of adversity	X ₂₂
I can recruit and train key employees	X ₂₃

Correlation Matrix

According to the information on the correlation matrix Table, twenty three variables (23) were included in the correlation matrix, each item loaded highest on the component were expected to belong to (in excess of 0.49). Using 50% bench mark; variables with correlation above 49% were noted with an asterisk. In Column XI, variable XI reported the highest relationship with Variable X2 (67%) indicating that ability to see new market opportunities for new products and service and discovering new ways to improve existing market were entrepreneurial skills that are highly correlated among the students. While Column X3, reported the highest number of correlated variables (X4, X5, X8 and X9). The determinant of the correlation matrix is 1.31E-0.05 which is above 0. This implies that correlation co-efficient between a variable and itself is 1. So, the principal diagonal of the correlation matrix contains 1s. The correlation co-efficient above and below the principal diagonal are the same. Hence, the results offered some evidence of distinct measure and this test passed the minimum standard for factor analysis to be conducted.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

To measure the sample adequacy and the test of sphericity, the study employed Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett's test of Sphericity.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.936
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.
	5.955E3
	253
	.000

Source: Author's computation using data from field survey

The information on KMO and Bartlett's Test indicated that Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin which measures the sample adequacy had a satisfactory result of 0.936 which was closer to 1 while Bartlett's Test of sphericity was significant because the probability was less than 0.05. Hence, the analysis needs to proceed because the sample adequacy had satisfied the necessary standard for factor analysis.

Communalities

This is the proportion of each variable variance that can be explained by all the factors jointly and it is the reliability of the indicator. Information on how much of the variance in the variables had been accounted for by the extracted factor

Table 3: Communities variables

Communalities	Initial (a)	Extraction (b)
X1	1.000	0.462
X2	1.000	0.545*
X3	1.000	0.585*
X4	1.000	0.596*
X5	1.000	0.552*
X6	1.000	0.561*
X7	1.000	0.527*
X8	1.000	0.573*
X9	1.000	0.491
X10	1.000	0.406
X11	1.000	0.394
X12	1.000	0.579*
X13	1.000	0.468
X14	1.000	0.515*
X15	1.000	0.287
X16	1.000	0.533*
X17	1.000	0.505*
X18	1.000	0.601*
X19	1.000	0.592*
X20	1.000	0.634*
X21	1.000	0.630*
X22	1.000	0.493
X23	1.000	0.446

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The information in the Table indicated that the values on (b) column implies the proportion of each 23 variables that can be explained by the factor, 15 variables out of the 23 variables indicated high variable variance representation which was above 0.5 explained by the

retained factors. Variable 20 and 21 with 0.634 and 0.630 were well represented in the common factor space while variable 15 with 0.287 was not well represented.

Total Variance Explained

Information on all the factors extractable from the factor analysis along with Eigen values, the percent of variance attributable to each factor, and the cumulative variance of the factor was presented in the table.

Initially all the variables were 23 before the factor analysis was employed, according to the information on the table, the total Eigen values showed that only three components had an explanatory importance because their values were greater than 1, therefore those values with less than 1 contributed little to the explanation of the variance in the variables and may be ignored as redundant with those of higher values. So, components less than 1 percent were not significant. The cumulative percentage of variance of the 3 components was 52.064 percent, while the common variance showed that only 3 components were retained. The rotation sums squared loadings showed that 5.783, 4.029 and 2.162 were the distribution of the variance while the cumulative percentage was 52.064 percent with cumulative variance of 25.146%, 17.519% and 9.399% were contributed by component 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

The Scree Plot

The Scree Plot graph was used to determine the variable to retain. Information on the Scree plot tests is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: The Scree Plot

From the figure above, the components were on the X axis and the corresponding Eigen values on the Y axis. The values on the Scree plot decrease from the factor number 1 to 2. From the third factor as one move to the right, towards later components, the Eigen values drop. This means only three factors have been retained, this is because the curve begins to flatten between 2 and 3.

Components (Factor) Matrix

The components matrix is obtainable after applying the varimax rotation which converged in 5 iterations, variables that are loaded onto each factor were selected taking 0.5 as the cut off point for explanatory purposes.

The factors had been re-named and the information on the component matrix is presented in the table 4 below

		Component		
s/n		1	2	3
1	X1	0.560		
2	X2	0.588		
3	X3	0.656		
4	X4	0.731		
5	X5	0.671		
6	X6	0.685		
7	X7	0.671		
8	X8	0.719		
9	X9	0.594		
10	X10	0.541		
11	X11	0.595		
12	X12	0.552		0.505
13	X13			0.675
14	X14			0.525
15	X15			0.502
16	X16		0.502	
17	X17		0.568	
18	X18		0.715	
19	X19		0.727	
20	X20		0.775	

Source: Author's computation using data from field survey

According to the information above, the table provided loading of the 20 variables on the three factors extracted. All the loading represented had values above 0.5, this means that loading less than 0.5 was already suppressed. The higher the absolute values of the loading, the more the factor attributes to the variable. The highest loading was X₂₀ with 0.775 which is components 1 while the lowest component was X₁₅ and X₁₆ with 0.502 on the component 2 and 3.

In conclusion, the result showed that out of the twenty three (23) entrepreneurial skills loaded into the factor analysis only three (3) which are identify as; ability to see opportunities for new products, discovering of new ways of improving on existing products and identifying new areas for potential growth which seems relevant for entrepreneurial skills among the students.

Economic Regression Interpretation

The econometric result is presented in table 5. The result is presented using 3 models. Model 1 presents the result of the demographic characteristics of the respondents, while model 2 added results of the contextual variables and the last model incorporated the physiological traits of the respondents. In model 1: the Log expression Chi² was 31.35 with 12 as degree of freedom, the level of significance was 0.0017, the log likelihood was -349.3 while the marginal effect for the dependent (Entrepreneurial intention) was 0.5189, In model 2 (which included the addition of contextual factor variables to the model 1, the purpose was to ascertain the effect of both demographic and contextual factors on entrepreneurial intention) the result showed that; the Log likelihood was -308.3 and the marginal effect of the

dependent variable was 0.5252 and finally, model 3 (which included the addition of Psychological traits variables to model 2) the logistic regression showed that; Log regression Chi^2 was 114.18, and the marginal effect increased slightly to 0.5253. This shows that Psychological traits do not have much predicting effect on the entrepreneurial intention of the undergraduates. The models were all significant at 99 percent confidence level.

According to information on Table 5, our logistic results show that gender seems to have a significant role in the model. The males were found with a higher probability of taking to self-employment than females and this was significant at 95 percent confidence level. The result from the marginal impact shows that the degree of responsiveness of males to entrepreneurship relative to females is 10.1 per cent in model 1 and this increased to 13.9 in both model 2 and 3. This means that males manifest greater propensity to establish their own businesses, this confirms the findings of many earlier studies.

The result of the original impact suggests that the degree of responsiveness of 19.87 percent in model 1 and it increases to 22 per cent to model 2 and 22.3 percent in model 3. There was the need to exercise some caution for the result of the free thinker because the number of respondents in the whole sample was very small. This conclusion does not find support in a study in Britain concluded that Muslims, Hindus and Sikhs had significantly higher probabilities of being self-employed than Christians. Family position seems also to play a role in influencing the students towards entrepreneurial related activities. The Third born was found to possess less probability of taking to self-employment after graduation compared to the first born students and this was significant at 90 percent confidence level. The marginal impact results suggest that the degree of responsiveness of third born to self employment relative to first born is 12 per cent in model 1 and this increase to 14 per cent in both models 2 and 3.

Further, Institutions seem to play some roles in influencing undergraduates towards entrepreneurship. OAU students were found to possess a lower probability of taking to self-employment after graduation compared to their counterparts in UNN and this was significant at 99 percent confidence level in model 2 and model 3. The marginal impact results suggest that the degree if responsiveness of OAU to self-employment compared to FUTA was lower by 33 per cent. Further, students from UNIBADAN were found with a lower probability of becoming self-employment compare to FUTA and this was significant at 95 percent confidence level. The marginal impact suggests a degree of responsiveness of 24 percent less than FUTA in models 2 and 3.

From the result, department seems to play an important role in influencing the students towards entrepreneurship. Students from Geography were found to possess a lower probability of taking to self-employment after graduation compared to students from Economics department and this is also significant at 95 percent confidence level. The marginal impact suggests that Geography students' response by 19.5 percent less to Economics student model 2 and model 3. Moreover, Political Science Students were found to possess a lower probability of taking to self-employment after graduation compared to Economics students and this is significant at 99 percent confidence level. The marginal impacts suggest that the degree of responsiveness of Political Science students towards self-employment relative to Economics students was 38 percent less than that those of Economics in both models 2 and 3. Sociology students were found to possess lower probability of taking to self employment after graduation compared to students from Economics department and this is significant at 99 percent confidence level. The marginal impact suggests a degree of responsiveness of 27 percent less in both models 2 and 3, while students from Psychology

department were the only ones that seem to possess a higher probability of taking to entrepreneurship compared to their Economics counterpart. However, this was not significant.

The role of job prospects after graduation on entrepreneurial intention shows that students with prospects of securing jobs with the Federal Government were not willing to opt for self-employment after graduation and this was significant at 90 percent confidence level. The marginal impact suggests that the probability of students with prospect in Civil Service after graduation is 0.12 percent model 2 and model 3. From this conclusion, it seems that the higher reward in form of corruption among public servant may be responsible for the decline in entrepreneurial intention among those who had the intention in working in federal own ministries. This shows that working in federal government ministries is more rewarding than becoming self-employed.

The influence of Class of Degree of the students as a determinant of entrepreneurial intentions was examined. The result showed that students that were on Second Class Division and below had a higher and significant probability of becoming self-employed than those on First Class and this was significant at 90 percent confidence level. The marginal impact showed that the degree of responsiveness of students in this group to entrepreneurial intention compared to those of first class as 16.4 percent and 16.5 percent in models 2 and 3 respectively. From this conclusion, it seems those with Second Class Lower and below were more entrepreneurial inclined due to the fact that those Second Class and lower may possess lesser prospects in securing job in high income paying establishment.

Further, information on the role of experience seems to suggest that those with prior experience in self-employment are less willing to go into self-employment after graduation and this was significant at 90 percent confidence level. The marginal impact results show that the degree of students with experience in self-employment was 12 percent in both models 2 and 3 compared to those with family business experience it was not found to be a significant factor influencing self-employment among undergraduates. From this result, we cannot really explain why this is so, but this may not be unconnected with the fact that running private businesses could be very expensive and highly risky.

The impact of entrepreneurship education was operationalized by asking the respondents to provide their evaluation of the usefulness of entrepreneurship education. Those who believed it was useful and very useful were collapsed into a dummy variable 1 (one) while those who did not believe were subsequently collapsed into 0 (zero). This was subsequently incorporated into our regression model. The results show that even though students who believed that the course was quite useful had a higher probability of becoming entrepreneur, however this was not statistically significant. Ideally, we would have expected that entrepreneurship education will induce a significant entrepreneurial behaviour among the students. However, it turns out to be a significant. This does not support the study of Ekpoh and Edet, (2018), who conducted a study among undergraduates in two tertiary schools in Akwa-Ibom and Cross-River State and concluded that taking course entrepreneurship influences career intention of tertiary school students’.

Lastly, factors such as Age Group, Family Size, Ethnic and Psychological traits employed in the model seem not to be significant factor influencing entrepreneurial intention among undergraduates in Nigeria.

	MODEL 1		MODEL 2		MODEL 3	
		$\frac{dy}{dx}$		$\frac{dy}{dx}$		$\frac{dy}{dx}$
GENDER	0.0405 0.1851	0.1009* 0.0458	0.5616 0.2059	0.1394** 0.0505	0.5588 0.2061	0.1387** 0.0506
RELIGION	0.8102 0.2305	0.1990*** 0.0543	0.3318 0.2853	0.0827 0.0709	0.3218 0.2867	0.0803 0.0713
FREE THINKER	0.7872 0.3744	0.1965* 0.0934	0.8824 0.3899	0.2200* 0.0972	0.8941 0.3923	0.2230 0.0978
AGE 1 (UNDER 20)	0.2791 0.4101	0.0690 0.0998	0.5632 0.4456	0.1357 0.1015	0.5591 0.4477	0.1348 0.1021
AGE 3 (30-40)	-0.0307 0.1994	-0.0077 0.0498	-0.0666 0.2223	-0.0166 0.0555	-0.0598 0.2241	-0.0149 0.0559
AGE 4 (ABOVE40)	-0.5268 0.5984	-0.1300 0.1428	-0.04654 0.6733	-0.1154 0.1633	-0.4332 0.6770	-0.1076 0.1651
SECOND BORN	-0.9389 0.2048	-0.0234 0.0511	-0.0389 0.2262	-0.1387* 0.0646	-0.0560 0.2274	-0.0139 0.0567
THIRD BORN	-0.4731 0.2434	-1176* 0.0597	-0.5587 0.2649	0.0144 0.0687	-0.5566 0.2668	-0.1381* 0.0651
LOG(FAMILY SIZE)	0.0405 0.02460	0.0101 0.0614	0.0578 0.2753	-0.0698 0.08	0.0686 0.2785	0.0171 0.0695
YORUBA	0.26624 0.2131	0.0654 0.0529	-0.2801 0.3221	0.0777 0.1130	-0.2649 0.3239	-0.0660 0.0805
HAUSA	-0.3142 0.3408	-0.0783 0.0844	0.3155 0.4673	-0.0885 0.1017	0.3167 0.4696	0.0780 0.1135
OTHER MINORITIES	-0.1529 0.3529	-0.0382 0.0881	-0.3351 0.4116	-0.0097 0.0564	-0.3558 0.4153	-0.0887 0.1026
PARENTAL INFLUENCE			0.1839 0.2340	0.0459 0.0584	0.1628 0.2376	0.0407 0.0593
OAU			-1.3965 0.3146	-0.3329*** 0.0677	-1.3926 0.3169	-0.3321*** 0.0682
UNIBADAN			-0.9843 0.3311	-0.2411** 0.0776	-0.9668 0.3341	-0.2370** 0.0786
GEOGRAPHY			-0.7936 0.3008	-0.1950** 0.0710	-0.7919 0.3051	-0.1946** 0.0721
POLITICAL SCIENCES			-1.6575 0.3002	-0.3849*** 0.0596	-1.6574 0.3026	-0.3850*** 0.0601
PSYCHOLOGY			-0.1941 0.3504	-0.0485 0.0875	-0.1765 0.3514	-0.0441 0.0877
SOCIOLOGY			-1.1231 0.3353	-0.2683*** 0.0723	-1.1230 0.3514	-0.2683*** 0.0728
BANK			0.0150 0.2733	0.0037 0.0681	-0.0071 0.2755	-0.0018 0.0687
FED CIVIL SERVICE			0.4735 0.2331	-0.1178* 0.0574	-0.4895 0.2349	-0.1218 0.0578
PARENTAL BIZ			0.0276 0.2150	0.0069 0.0545	0.0345 0.2199	0.0086 0.0548
ENTREPRENEURSHIIP EDUCATION 3			0.0083 0.2540	0.0021 0.0634	0.0174 0.2680	0.0043 0.0669
2 ND CLASS UPPER			0.2945 0.3433	0.0734 0.0854	0.2963 0.3438	0.0739 0.0855
2 ND LOWER CLASS/ THIRD/ PASS			0.6760 0.3855	0.1644* 0.0900	0.6819 0.3865	0.1658 0.0901
FAMILY BUSINESS			0.3523 0.2110	0.0872 0.0545	0.3621 0.2231	0.0896 0.0546
SELF-EMPLOYMENT			-0.4903 0.2108	-0.1219* 0.0519	-0.4906 0.2109	-0.1220* 0.0520

CREATIVITY					-0.0378 0.2278	-0.0094 0.0471
INNOVATION					0.0255 0.1890	0.0064 0.0568
RISK					0.1244 0.1838	0.0310 0.0459
LEADERSHIP					-0.1186 0.1626	-0.0296 0.0406

Note: $\frac{dy}{dx}$ is for discrete change of dummy variable from '0' to '1'. (***) denotes 99% level of significant, (**) denotes 95% level of significant, (*) denotes 90%.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study has sought to understand the determinants of entrepreneurship intentions among the undergraduate students in Nigeria with a particular emphasis on the role played by entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial intention. This area of study has commanded tremendous attention in recent time due to the role of an entrepreneur as a stimulator of economic growth, reducing the rate of unemployment, creates new market, and also promotes technological innovation. However, findings emanated from the study showed that students possess greater entrepreneurial competencies in three major areas; which include identifying business opportunity, networking and risk taking out of the twenty three entrepreneurial skills identifies.

Majority of the students responded that entrepreneurship education was useful. While in term of job prospects, after graduation, a good number of the students opted for privately owned establishment. Finally, the study shows that students' entrepreneurial intention was not really motivated by entrepreneurship education. In conclusion, this study does not validate the previous studies in Nigeria, that indicated that entrepreneurship education promotes entrepreneurial intention among undergraduates.

Recommendations

The major motivation of this study is to examine the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions most especially the role played by entrepreneurship education which has become an instrument in promoting entrepreneurial behaviour among undergraduates in tertiary institutions. Unfortunately, as showed by this study, entrepreneurship education was not a significant determinant of students' entrepreneurial intention. The implication of this is that, the introduction of entrepreneurship education may not be driven force for students taken to entrepreneurial activities after graduation. Therefore, for entrepreneurship education to be a variable instrument of promoting entrepreneurial intention among the graduates, youth, the following recommendations are suggested.

1. There is need for the government to produce the conducive environment for the growth of entrepreneurial related activities. In other words, the government should concentrate more in the provision of infrastructural facilities such as; good road networks, modern health facilities, stable political system, unbiased judicial system, safe air transport system and most importantly, adequate and stable power supply. With all these in place, the production of entrepreneurship education will yield the desired objectives.
2. The above recommendation necessarily, calls for a consistent and determined government to create a Ministry of Entrepreneurship Development. This ministry will be staffed with officials who thoroughly understand the need for promoting entrepreneurship among the youth in all the institutions in the country on the role and reward of becoming self employed.

3. In order to encourage the youth, a total overhauling is highly needed in civil service. It is suggested that government should introduce a reform that will enable the wages of civil servants to be determined by market forces. This will not only encourage increase in productivity but also discourage those with entrepreneurial intention from applying for paid jobs.
4. The study has shown that reward is a factor to be considered if entrepreneurship activities should be promoted. Hence, the government needs to make entrepreneurship rewarding by creating enable environment for it to drive. The promotion of entrepreneurial intention among the youth should not be government programme alone. Stakeholders such as religion bodies, Non-Governmental Agencies (NGOs), communities etc should also work hand-in-hand with the government in making entrepreneurial development a reality. It is therefore suggested that that a platform such as seminars, conferences, workshops, talk shows, etc need to be incorporated into the school curriculum so as to provide sensitization on the prospect of becoming self employed among the undergraduates.

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